

README

This data repository supports a manuscript by Luwei Yang, Maxim Nikurashin, Andrew McC. Hogg, and Bernadette M. Sloyan, submitted to Geophysical Research Letters.

This repository contains the processed data that support the figures in the manuscript. We refer the readers to Yang et al. (2021) for a detailed description of model configuration and the repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5225613>) for other data files needed to reproduce the results.

List of data files

- **Figure 1**
 - Forcing files used in the wind perturbation experiments.
 - Wind stress magnitude of 0.1 N m^{-2} : [forcing_w1.nc](#)
 - Wind stress magnitude of 0.2 N m^{-2} : [forcing_w2.nc](#)
 - Wind stress magnitude of 0.3 N m^{-2} : [forcing_w3.nc](#)
- **Figure 2**
 - The meridional transect of the time- and zonal-mean density.
 - Reference case: [time_zonal_mean_density_3winds_reference.nc](#)
 - Lee wave case: [time_zonal_mean_density_3winds_leewaves.nc](#)
- **Figure 3**
 - Time-mean eddy kinetic energy
 - Reference case (wind stress magnitude of 0.1 N m^{-2}): [EKE_lin_cd3_w1.nc](#)
 - Reference case (wind stress magnitude of 0.2 N m^{-2}): [EKE_lin_cd3_w2.nc](#)
 - Reference case (wind stress magnitude of 0.3 N m^{-2}): [EKE_lin_cd3_w3.nc](#)
 - Lee wave case (wind stress magnitude of 0.1 N m^{-2}): [EKE_lee_wave_w1.nc](#)
 - Lee wave case (wind stress magnitude of 0.2 N m^{-2}): [EKE_lee_wave_w2.nc](#)
 - Lee wave case (wind stress magnitude of 0.3 N m^{-2}): [EKE_lee_wave_w3.nc](#)
 - Time-mean bottom-500m-averaged stratification in the reference case
 - Wind stress magnitude of 0.1 N m^{-2} : [b5N_lin_cd3_w1.mat](#)
 - Wind stress magnitude of 0.2 N m^{-2} : [b5N_lin_cd3_w2.mat](#)
 - Wind stress magnitude of 0.3 N m^{-2} : [b5N_lin_cd3_w3.mat](#)
 - Time series of lee wave drag coefficient and bottom-500m-averaged stratification in the lee wave case (last 5 years of the model output)
 - Lee wave case (wind stress magnitude of 0.1 N m^{-2}): [lee_wave_coeff_b5N_w1.nc](#)
 - Lee wave case (wind stress magnitude of 0.2 N m^{-2}): [lee_wave_coeff_b5N_w2.nc](#)
 - Lee wave case (wind stress magnitude of 0.3 N m^{-2}): [lee_wave_coeff_b5N_w3.nc](#)

References

Yang, L., Nikurashin, M., McC. Hogg, A., & Sloyan, B. M. (2021). The impact of lee waves on the Southern Ocean circulation. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 51(9), 2933-2950.